

DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR COMPETENCES IN THE TRAINING OF IT TEACHERS FOR SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS

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According to A.M. Pishkalo, the construction of a methodical system of teaching, aimed at forming the readiness of the computer teacher to implement differentiation based on specialization, consists in the development of five interrelated elements of the training course. Initially, external goals are formed in accordance with the modern/current needs of society and the educational system (social order) in the training of an informatics teacher in a specialized school. Based on the social order, the internal goals of the training course are formulated/expressed in terms of compliance with the structure of the professional activity of the specialized school teacher and compliance with other elements of the methodical system. When setting/determining goals, we take into account the concept we have developed, the main principles and approaches of teaching that are highlighted in it [1].

Based on the set goals, we determine the components of the professional competence of a specialized school informatics teacher, and choose the content, forms, methods and tools of teaching according to them.

Technologies for choosing teaching content, teaching forms, methods and tools, using mathematical methods to distinguish the conceptual directions of the content, building its logical structure and optimization, allow to get different interpretations of the OMT built taking into account real conditions (the number of hours to study the course, the profile of students/ preparation in issues of organizing classification based on specialization, individual abilities of teachers or mentors of higher educational institutions, etc.).

The specification/distinctive feature of training in profile/specialty areas based on specialization in informatics is the need to organize training taking into account variability/variability, which consists in the separation, design and implementation of profiled/specialized, basic, profiled/specialized courses and related courses and elective courses. As a result of specialized education/teaching, it is necessary for the student to define his/her own destiny/future according to the profile/specialty and be ready to continue studying at a higher educational institution.

In order to determine the components of the professional competence of a profiled/specialized school informatics teacher, first of all, the list of special competencies, we suggest starting with the professional tasks that describe the

activity of this specialist. Among them, we distinguish the following and clarify them:

Design individual learning trajectories for students that provide variety/variability and individualization of the learning process.

Designing and implementation of profiled/specialized, in-depth, basic, elective courses of informatics for classes of different profiles/specialties, taking into account specialized educational goals and age characteristics of students.

Provide practical orientation of the learning process by introducing interactive, activity-based components.

Establish interaction with other subjects of the educational process, implement a network model of specialized education in the resource center.

Creating an educational and informational environment of the profiled/specialized school and using their capabilities to consciously select the profile of the school's students and achieve the educational goals of the profiled/specialized school.

To ensure that secondary school students determine their destiny/future by profile/specialty and develop the skills and competencies necessary for continuous education in the relevant vocational field.

The subjects of general humanitarian, socio-economic, mathematical and natural science cycles constitute the invariance/constancy of the information culture of any teacher and are intended for the formation and development of key competencies. In addition, the sciences of mathematical and natural science cycles (with the foundations of mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, ecology) are closely related to the science we are studying (informatics), they actively use informatics methods, and they require the study of informatics in a specialized way. Consequently, the formation of the key competencies of an informatics teacher in a specialized school is based on the subjects of this cycle.

General professional sciences implement the psychological, pedagogical and general methodical directions of teacher training. In studying the subjects of this cycle, the foundations of the professional activity of any teacher are laid, that is, the key competencies are formed and developed, which play the role of basic competencies for the formation of the professional competence of a computer science teacher of a specialized school, and which we develop by organizing education according to the educational elements that are highlighted later.

The formation of special competencies of the informatics teacher on the basis of the developed basic competence is carried out in the study of the subjects of the basic school informatics teacher's subject and special methodical training. These

competencies play a key role in the conditions of training of an informatics teacher in a specialized school, and they serve as a basis for the formation and development of special competencies for solving professional problems in specialized education.

List of references:

1. Pyshkalo, A. M. Methodological system of training geometry in primary school: autoref. dis. ... Dr. Ped. Nauk: 13.00.02 / A. M. Pyshkalo. - M., 1975. - 32 p

